

A high performance laser induced graphene (LIG) dual biosensor for simultaneous monitoring of glucose and lactate

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ABSTRACT

The growing demand for efficient and reliable biosensors has driven significant advancements in the development of innovative platforms for real-time monitoring of key biomarkers. In this work, we developed a novel dual biosensing platform designed for simultaneous detection of glucose and lactate, leveraging a laser scribing technology. Individual glucose and lactate biosensors were firstly fabricated, using three electrode designs and Laser Induced Graphene (LIG) as transduction electrode. The individual biosensors displayed high linear range in the relevant sweat physiological range, good sensitivity (41.1 and $12.4 \mu\text{A mM}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$ for glucose and lactate, respectively), Limit of Detection (LOD, $14.9 \mu\text{M}$ and 2.4mM for glucose and lactate) and superior short- and long-term stability. Following optimization and in-depth characterization of the individual platforms, a dual sensing platform was designed to offer robust and reliable simultaneous detection of glucose and lactate in a single, integrated system. The dual biosensor maintained the performance displayed in single format, exhibiting sensitivities of $41.2 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2} \text{mM}^{-1}$ and $12.0 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2} \text{mM}^{-1}$ for glucose and lactate, respectively. The dual platform was successfully tested in artificial sweat, demonstrating its potential for precise and reliable biomarker monitoring in continuous health monitoring systems and point-of-care diagnostic.

1. Introduction

Over the last decade, there has been remarkable progress in wearable sensor technology, driven by the increasing need for non-invasive, personalized, and point-of-care monitoring (Bariya et al., 2018; Sempronatto et al., 2020). Significantly, there has been a substantial expansion in research efforts aimed the realization of diagnostic devices for the detection of crucial biomarkers, particularly those found in sweat (Backiyalakshmi et al., 2024; S. Zhang et al., 2024a,b). Lactate and glucose are particularly important biomarkers, as they play dual roles in the body. On one hand, they are essential for energy production and metabolic functions, contributing to the performance and endurance of athletes. On the other hand, elevated levels of glucose and/or lactate can also signal potential health issues, such as metabolic disorders and other diseases, highlighting the significance of the development of sensing

platforms for the monitoring of athletic performance and overall health status (Hall et al., 2016; Li et al., 2022; Vekic et al., 2022).

Electrochemical enzymatic biosensors are notable for their high sensitivity, selectivity, low-cost, and ease of miniaturization compared to other sensor types (Wu et al., 2023). Despite the large available literature on single electrochemical sensing platforms (Boeva et al., 2024), there are very few examples of integrating these sensors into a unified dual-biosensing platform (Asaduzzaman et al., 2023; Gao et al., 2016; Lei et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2023). Key challenges include not only complexity, data accuracy, and device miniaturization but also issues related to sensor stability, interferences, and long-term reliability (Gao et al., 2016). Carbon-based materials are excellent candidates in the development of biosensors due to their excellent electrical conductivity, biocompatibility, and ability to facilitate electron transfer, which are essential for enhancing sensor performance (Liu

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et al., 2024). Among the diverse technologies available for the fabrication of carbonaceous structures as transducing elements on flexible substrates, Direct Laser Writing (DLW) has recently emerged as a high throughput and energy efficient method. In this method conductive Laser Induced Graphene, LIG, patterns of customizable shape and micrometer size scale are readily produced without the need of masks or chemicals. The resulting LIG electrode materials display high catalytic properties and electrochemical performance associated to their high surface area and defect-rich morphology, making them ideal for electrochemical applications. Furthermore, DLW offers opportunities for scalability, due to its integrability into roll-to-roll production lines.

Several reports have demonstrated the successful use of DLW technologies for the fabrication of glucose and/or lactate biosensors (Bauer et al., 2021a; Gao et al., 2022; Garland et al., 2023; Hamidi et al., 2023; Hjort et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2023; Madden et al., 2022; Meng et al., 2022; Pinheiro et al., 2021; Settu et al., 2021; Zahed et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2024a,b). However, significant challenges remain in terms of sensitivity, biofunctionalization, and comprehensive performance evaluation. Most reported LIG-based biosensors utilize expensive laser sources, which limit scalability and practical implementation. Additionally, while high sensitivity has been achieved in some studies, it often requires the incorporation of nanomaterials such as noble metal nanoparticles and carbon nanotubes, increasing fabrication complexity and cost. Despite these enhancements, achieving incredibly high sensitivity without additional nanomaterial modifications remains rare, and in the few exceptional cases where it has been reported (Garland et al., 2023; Settu et al., 2021), the biosensors operate at relatively high potentials, increasing the risk of interference from electroactive species in complex biofluids such as sweat and thus limiting their practical applicability. Another critical challenge is the lack of a standardized biofunctionalization method, leading to inconsistencies in sensor performance and limited reproducibility. Moreover, previous reports often lack a comprehensive analytical assessment, making it difficult to directly compare results and establish benchmarks for performance evaluation. On the other side, most of these studies have focused on the optimization of the LIG production process on different substrates as well as on the development of electrode modification strategies to improve the performance of transducing functions, with the aim to integrate all the desired analytical features into single analyte detection devices. Consequently, there are a very few examples of LIG-based dual mode sensing platforms for glucose and lactate (Bauer et al., 2021a; Garland et al., 2023). In addition, data related to short- and long-term stability of developed single or multiplex biosensors, crucial enable for future incorporation of LIG-based biosensors into wearable and POC devices, have rarely been undertaken (Liu et al., 2023; Zahed et al., 2020). For example, it is known that LIG features produced by infrared laser irradiation are mechanically weak, as LIG flakes can detach from the flexible surface upon repeated use or bending cycles. Recently, different stabilization strategies have been presented, including the use of Au clusters/chitosan composites (Zhang et al., 2022), combination of ultraviolet laser pretreatment and infrared laser defocused processing¹⁹, modification of the LIG surface with a conductive polymer²⁶. However, these require additional fabrication steps and can potentially affect the effectiveness of the biomodification steps. Therefore, it is desirable to develop easier strategies to stabilize LIG electrodes to achieve long-term stability. The second stage in biosensor construction involves electrode biofunctionalization and the development of an encapsulation matrix. This step facilitates deliberate integration of various components into the structure, thereby enhancing the performance of the biological recognition element and strengthening interaction with the graphitic electrodes for improved robustness. Chitosan (CS) and bovine serum albumin (BSA) are extensively utilized in biosensor fabrication, due to their stabilizing effect as well as biocompatibility (Suginta et al., 2013). More importantly, since these compounds contain functional groups with oxygen and nitrogen, their application is particularly suited to the carbonaceous nature of electrode materials, leveraging their rich

chemistry with and their ability to form hydrogels, which further enhances the biosensor's functionality and stability. Although these hydrogels have been extensively used in biosensor construction on conventional substrates, their optimization and integration with LIG materials have not yet been fully explored.

This work presents the development of high performance, robust and stable LIG glucose and lactate biosensors, achieved through careful design and optimization of the LIG electrode fabrication conditions and biofunctionalization protocols. Specifically, the performance of the individual biosensing platforms was optimized through application of a systematic approach whereby DLW parameters including laser wavelength, power, speed, resolution and distance were carefully adjusted to produce mechanically stable and low sheet resistance LIG electrodes. Following this phase, a systematic optimization of the biofunctionalization matrix was carried out, for both glucose and lactate. This resulted in fabrication of biosensors displaying superior performance including high sensitivity, high selectivity, and short- and long-term stabilities. Finally, the invaluable know-how gained during the optimization process of individual platforms was applied to the realization of dual biosensors enabling the concomitant detection of glucose and lactate. The dual platform displayed performance comparable to that of the individual sensors, maintaining the same efficacy for both analytes. Our findings demonstrate a scalable and reproducible strategy for fabricating LIG biosensors with significant potential for real-world applications in wearable and point-of-care diagnostics.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Reagents and chemicals

Glucose oxidase (GOx) type VII (EC 1.1.3.4, *Aspergillus niger*, 221 U mg⁻¹, G2133), chitosan (CS, medium molecular weight, 448877), bovine serum albumin (BSA), glutaraldehyde (25 %W/W, 354400), Nafion perfluorinated resin (5 %W/W, 527084), tetrathiafulvalene (183180), L-sodium lactate (L7022), D(+)-glucose (G5767), Ag|AgCl paste (60/40, 901773) were purchased from sigma-Aldrich. L-Lactate oxidase (LOx) (EC 1.13.12.4, microorganism, 101 U mg⁻¹) was purchased from Sorachim SA (LCO-301).

2.2. Biosensors fabrication

2.2.1. Laser induced graphene electrodes fabrication

Prior to biofunctionalization, three-electrode patterns, consisting of a circular working electrode (WE, 3 mm diameter), a counter electrode (CE), and a reference electrode (RE), were fabricated using the direct laser writing technique. These patterns were written on the surface of a polyimide tape (approximately 70 μm thick) affixed to a glass slide. For this purpose, a laser with a power of 5 W and an illumination wavelength of 450 nm was utilized (Laser Pecker2 handheld engraver). The values of optimum settings were as 2k for resolution, 14 % for power (% of 5 W), 14 % for depth (or writing speed), and a defocusing distance of 5 mm. To eliminate the residue of carbonaceous particles, after fabrication the entire surface of the electrodes was sequentially washed with acetone, isopropyl alcohol, and deionized water. Then, a drop of Ag|AgCl paste was applied on the surface of the RE and dried at 100 °C for about 10 min. Finally, the LIG WE was modified with tetrathiafulvalene (TTF) through the drop-casting of 2 μl from a 10 mg ml⁻¹ ethanolic solution (LIG/TTF).

2.2.2. Fabrication of glucose and lactate biosensors

To construct the biosensors, solutions containing the relevant enzymes were first prepared. For glucose biosensor, the optimum medium was prepared by gentle mixing of equal volumes of GOx (5 U μl⁻¹ in PBS), BSA (10 mg ml⁻¹ in PBS) and CS (1 % W/V in acetic acid 1 % V/V). For lactate biosensor, the optimum encapsulation matrix was composed of LOx (20 μl, 5 U μl⁻¹), BSA (100 μl, 25 mg ml⁻¹), GA (10 μl, 2.5 %).

Then, the surface of a LIG-modified TTF WE electrode was fully covered with 10 μl of the enzyme solution and allowed to dry at room temperature. Subsequently, 5 μl Nafion were drop-casted on the enzyme immobilized electrode and left to dry at room temperature (LIG/TTF/GOx/Nafion and LIG/TTF/LOx/Nafion). The fabricated biosensors were stored in the fridge.

2.3. Characterization

The morphology of the LIG surface was investigated via scanning electron microscopy (Zeiss 16 SUPRA 35 VP operating at 5 kV). The LIG Raman characteristics were investigated using a Horiba XploRA Raman microscope equipped with a 70 mW, 532 nm laser. Sheet resistance (R_{sh}) of LIG was measured with a Fluke 179 true rms multimeter from LIG rectangular features (3 mm \times 18 mm). Voltammetric and amperometric measurements were performed using an Autolab potentiostat PGSTAT204 (Metrohm, Utrecht, Netherlands) with a three-electrode design. The responses of the biosensors were recorded in a flow injection analysis (FIA) system, which comprised of a homemade 3D-printed wall-jet flow cell, a peristaltic pump, a manual six-port injection valve, and PVC tubing (0.889 mm i.d.).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Laser induced graphene (LIG) sensors: fabrication and characterization

LIG sensors were fabricated by direct laser scribing of polyimide following a systematic optimization of the writing process whereby the laser wavelength, resolution, defocusing distance, power, and depth were adjusted following a procedure described in detail in Fig. S1. First of all, a visible laser was selected for LIG fabrication, based on the superior mechanical characteristics displayed by the resulting LIG upon several bending cycles, compared to CO_2 -laser produced LIG structures (Fig. S2). A final laser power of 14 %, laser depth of 14 % and defocusing distance of 5 mm were selected as writing conditions. Electrical

characterization showed that these writing conditions produced LIG materials of reproducible and low sheet resistance (R_{sh}) equal to 13 Ωsq^{-1} . Electrochemical characterization showed that electrochemical peak separation ($\Delta E_p = E_{\text{pa}} - E_{\text{pc}}$) in cyclic voltammograms (CVs) was approximately 62 mV, indicating a near-Nernstian behavior.

Following writing conditions optimization, the LIG morphology was characterized by electron microscopy. Fig. 1a–b shows SEM images of LIG, displaying the high surface area and high density of defects typical of laser scribed graphitic materials (Vaughan et al., 2020). The SEM image of Fig. 1c shows the surface of LIG following drop-casting of TTF, revealing homogeneous and large area coverage. The Raman spectrum of LIG (Fig. 1d) displayed the characteristic of graphitic materials with D, G, and 2D peaks centered at 1341 (defects in graphene), 1579 (sp^2 carbon stretching), and 2682 (second order zone-boundary phonons) cm^{-1} , respectively. The $I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$ ratio was 1.1 (± 0.2) was associated with the high disorder and heterogeneity, the $I_{2\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$ ratio was 0.5 (± 0.1) and was related to the presence of multilayer graphene structures (Tiliakos et al., 2016). The electrochemical behavior of LIG was investigated by cyclic voltammetry using the three-electrode design shown in Fig. 1e. Fig. 1f shows the CVs recorded at different scan rates (10–100 mV) in a ferricyanide solution, displaying the anodic and cathodic peaks related to the redox system $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-/4-}$. The formal potential was 0.240 V vs. $\text{Ag}|\text{AgCl}, 0.1\text{M KCl}$ with a peak separation of 62 mV at a scan rate (ν) of 10 mV s^{-1} . The peak separations fell in a quasireversible region ($60 < \Delta E_p < 80 \text{ mV}, 10\text{--}100 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$).

3.2. Optimization and evaluation of analytical characteristics of the glucose biosensor

Before exploring the effect of the enzyme immobilization matrix, the concentration of TTF was optimized by drop-casting ethanolic solutions of various concentrations (0.1–15 mg ml^{-1}) on the LIG working electrode, followed by flow injection analysis (FIA) of the TTF-LIG electrochemical response, measured upon injection of 1 mM glucose solution. Fig. 2a showed a current density increase with the increasing amount of adsorbed TTF on the LIG surface. As TTF hardly dissolved at

Fig. 1. SEM images of LIG electrode surface taken at a) low and b) high magnification; c) SEM image of LIG electrode following biofunctionalization; d) Representative Raman spectrum of LIG; e) photographs of LIG-based single and dual-electrode platforms; f) cyclic voltammograms (CVs) of bare LIG in aqueous solution containing 5 mM $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ and 0.1 M KCl at different scan rates.

Fig. 2. Plot of current densities derived from FIA records of glucose biosensors versus a) TTF concentration, b) applied potential magnitude, c) GOx unit, d) BSA concentration, e) chitosan and f) Nafion percentages. Glucose concentration 1 mM, carrier solution; PBS. Flow rate; 1 ml min⁻¹.

Fig. 3. a) FIA records of three different glucose biosensors; b) Calibration curve for glucose in PBS buffer; c) Continuous flow analysis (CFA) of glucose with possible interfering components; d) Calibration curves for glucose in PBS solution and artificial sweat in relevant sweat concentration range; e) CFA record of 150 μM glucose over 2 h continuous monitoring; f) Histogram of glucose responses measured over 10 weeks.

concentrations higher than 10 mg ml^{-1} , this value was chosen to ensure both the highest and the most reproducible response of the biosensors. Next, the effect of the potential magnitude was investigated by varying potential from 0 to 200 mV vs. Ag|AgCl, KCl (0.1M). Fig. 2b shows that moving towards positive potential, the response of the biosensor increased up to 100 mV and then reached a plateau. Consequently, 150 mV was selected as the optimum applied potential. The enzyme matrix was then optimized. Fig. 2c shows the increasing of biosensor response upon increasing concentrations of GOx, from 0.1 to $5 \text{ U } \mu\text{l}^{-1}$, leading to the selection of GOx $5 \text{ U } \mu\text{l}^{-1}$ for further investigation. As the enzyme matrix was composed of chitosan and BSA, also the amount of these components was optimized. As depicted in Fig. 2d and e, the highest current intensities were observed for 1% chitosan and 10 mg ml^{-1} BSA, respectively. The concentration of the Nafion layer on the biosensor was varied from 0.25% to 1% (Fig. 2f). Despite the higher response at lower concentrations, 1% Nafion concentration was selected, due to its minimal impact on the sensor response and possibly its higher efficacy in blocking interfering substances.

Fig. S3a illustrates the CVs of the fabricated glucose biosensor in 0.05 M PBS containing 0.1 M KCl at a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} showing two broad anodic and cathodic peaks between -0.05 and $+0.15 \text{ V}$ vs. Ag|AgCl|KCl(3M), related to the redox couple, TTF^+/TTF (Hale et al., 1991). To examine the catalytic effect, the CVs of the biosensors were analyzed in the presence of 10 mM and 20 mM of glucose. It is clear the height of the anodic peaks increased while the cathodic peaks diminished, indicating the high catalytic activities of the biosensors towards glucose. Then, the optimized glucose biosensors were employed for the precise detection of glucose concentration in phosphate buffer (pH = 7) through the FIA system.

Fig. 3a presents FIA traces recorded for three different biosensors during successive injections of glucose standard solutions (ranging from 0.025 to 20 mM) into a PBS stream at a constant flow rate of 1 ml min^{-1} . The resulting plot of current density responses against glucose concentrations showed a clear linear relationship across the broad concentration range, resulting in sensitivity = $41.1 \text{ } \mu\text{A mM}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ ($R^2 = 0.9977$) (Fig. 3b). The biosensors achieved a LOD ($S/N = 3$) of $14.9 \text{ } \mu\text{M}$. Interference studies were carried out in the FIA system by injecting possible interfering substances, including urea, uric acid, ascorbic acid, and lactic acid (Fig. 3c). Except for ascorbic acid, which exhibited an approximate 15% change in the response, no alterations in the sensor responses were recorded in the presence of other substances. To test the applicability of the biosensor to measure glucose in complex matrices, FIA measurements were also performed in artificial sweat (AS). Fig. 3d shows the calibration curve obtained in artificial sweat, which almost exactly mirrored the performance observed in PBS medium. The slopes in PBS and AS were $41.2 \text{ } \mu\text{A cm}^{-2} \text{ mM}^{-1}$ and $37.3 \text{ } \mu\text{A cm}^{-2} \text{ mM}^{-1}$, respectively. Then the values of the slopes were compared using a paired *t*-test analysis (Andrade and Estévez-Pérez, 2014), and no significant

difference was observed at the $P = 0.05$ level. These observations reveal the promising characteristics of the developed biosensor compared to similar biosensors. The short- and long-term stability of the glucose biosensor response was also assessed. As observed in Fig. 3e, the sensor response remained constant over 2 h of glucose ($150 \text{ } \mu\text{M}$) continuous flow, which is indicative of the high operational stability of the biosensor. The sensor long-term stability was evaluated over a period of ten weeks, during which the biosensor, stored in a refrigerator, displayed excellent stability over eight weeks (Fig. 3f).

Table 1 reports a comparison with other reported LIG- and screen printed-based biosensors for glucose, showing that our developed biosensor displayed satisfactory analytical characteristics while also benefiting from a simple modification structure and low working potential.

3.3. Optimization and evaluation of analytical characteristics of the lactate biosensor

To construct the lactate biosensor, the LIG working electrode was modified with the same optimal amount of TTF (10 mg ml^{-1}) previously used for the glucose biosensor. Due to the identical detection mechanism of both biomarkers, based on the oxidation of TTF on the LIG surface, the applied potential was also set to 150 mV. Unlike the glucose biosensor, for lactate the matrix composed of chitosan failed to show reproducible responses, which aligns with similar findings in the literature (Curran et al., 2018). Therefore, a medium comprising only BSA was selected to immobilize LOx, utilizing glutaraldehyde as a crosslinking agent. The comprehensive investigation of both BSA and glutaraldehyde concentrations revealed their crucial impact on the activity of LOx. Increasing the BSA solution concentration from 15 to 30 mg ml^{-1} at a 5% (w/w) GA concentration substantially extended the linear dynamic range (LDR) of the lactate calibration curve (Fig. S4a), albeit with a notable decrease in sensitivity (Fig. 4a). This behavior was attributed to the reduced enzyme affinity resulting from matrix encapsulation, which was further supported by the increase in the value of the Michaelis-Menten constant (K_M , see SI, Fig. S4b). Subsequently, the GA concentration was systematically varied from 0.1% to 7.5% (with BSA at 20 mg ml^{-1}), and the impact on both the LDR (Fig. S4c) and sensitivity (Fig. 4b) of the biosensor was investigated. Increasing the concentration of GA shifted the LDR to the submillimolar region, thus covering the lactate concentration range in sweat, although with a decrease in sensitivity (as well as increase of the K_M value, Fig. S4d). Therefore, varying concentrations of both BSA and GA enabled precise tuning of the LDR range and/or sensitivity to meet specific requirements. These observations indicate that the use of higher concentration of GA crosslinker renders the matrix more rigid, consequently limiting the enzyme's mobility, yet it provides significant sensitivity in detecting lactate levels within sweat ($5\text{--}20 \text{ mM}$ (Bariya et al., 2018)). Therefore, for sweat lactate analysis, the optimum

Table 1
Analytical characteristics of LIG- and screen printed-based glucose biosensors.

Composition of biosensing unit	Laser type	E_{app} mV	LDR mM	LOD μM	Sensitivity $\mu\text{A mM}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$	Ref
LIG						
PEDOT:PSS/Pt@Pd/GOx	CO ₂	–	0.003–9.2	3	247.3	Zahed et al. (2020)
PB/CS/GOx	CO ₂	–50	0–2	13.7	20.0	Bauer et al. (2021b)
GOx-CS	450 nm	+800	0–8	431	43.15	Settu et al. (2021)
PtNPs/PPD/GOx	CO ₂	+600	0–1	8	26.2	Garland et al. (2023)
PEDOT/AuNPs/GOx-GA	450 nm	+900	0.005–2.5	2	341.67	(Z. Zhang et al., 2024a,b)
Fc/GOx-BSA-GA	CO ₂	+100	0–11	0.004	11.3	Liu et al. (2023)
TTF/GOx-BSA-CS	450 nm	+150	0.025–20	14.6	41.1	this work
Screen/inject-printed						
PAni/PtNPs/GOx	–	+500	1–25	200	5.03	Li et al. (2018)
PB-CP/CS-SWCNTs/GOx-BSA	–	–100	0–1	20	18.41	Khosravi et al. (2023)

PB; Prussian Blue, Fc; ferrocene, PEDOT; poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene), PSS; polystyrene sulfonate, PPD; polyphenylenediamine. SWCNT; single-walled carbon nanotubes.

Fig. 4. Plot of current densities derived from FIA records of lactate biosensors versus a) BSA concentration, b) GA, and c) LOx unit; d) FIA responses of lactate biosensors at different concentrations of lactate. (inset: lactate calibration curve); e) Continuous flow analysis (CFA) of lactate with possible interfering components; f) Calibration curves in PBS solution and AS.

composition of matrix was selected as 20 mg ml^{-1} BSA and 5.0 % GA. Thereafter, the effect of the LOx units on the electrode surface was investigated from 0.5 to 6.5 $\text{U } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$. Fig. 4c shows that the biosensor reached maximum response for concentrations above 5 $\text{U } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$.

Similar to the glucose biosensor, the electrochemical characterization of this biosensor showed catalytic behavior towards lactate (Fig. S3b). Fig. 4d depicts the calibration curve recorded in the FIA system (in PBS buffer) for three lactate biosensors constructed following the optimization reported above. The response exhibited linearity within the 4–20 mM concentration range, with a sensitivity of 12.4 $\mu\text{A mM}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$ and a correlation coefficient of 0.9958 (Fig. 4d, inset). The LOD ($S/N = 3$) was calculated as 2.4 mM. The lactate sensors displayed good operational stability over a 2-h exposure to 10 mM lactate (Fig. S5a). The biosensor also showed good long-term stability over a 4-week period while being stored in the fridge (Fig. S5b). Next, the high selectivity of the sensor was tested in a continuous flow line by introduction of lactate (5 mM, in PBS) followed by the injection of AsA (10

μM), Glu (150 μM), UA (50 μM), and urea (4.5 mM). Fig. 4e shows that none of the tested species exhibited any interference with the lactate response. Finally, the biosensor's response was measured in both PBS solution and AS containing lactate concentrations ranging from 7.5 to 17.5 mM (Fig. 4f). The slopes were calculated as 12.2 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2} \text{mM}^{-1}$ in PBS and 11.9 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2} \text{mM}^{-1}$ in AS. Despite a slight difference in responses, comparing the slopes of both calibration curves in PBS and AS using paired *t*-test showed no significant difference ($P = 0.05$). This result indicates the capability of the proposed lactate biosensor for real sweat analysis.

The lactate biosensor, as shown in Table 2, exhibited satisfactory analytical characteristics comparable to other existing LIG-based and screen-printed devices. Notably, it incorporates all the advantages of these technologies and demonstrating its detection capabilities covered the entire range of lactate levels in sweat with very good sensitivity at a lower applied potential.

Table 2
Analytical characteristics of LIG based lactate biosensors on PI platforms.

Composition of biosensing unit	Laser type	E_{app} mV	LDR mM	LOD μM	Sensitivity $\mu\text{A mM}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$	Ref
LIG						
TTF/LOx-GA/CS	CO_2	+400	0–32	0.22	2.47×10^{-3}	Garland et al. (2023)
TTF/PtNPs/LOx-CS	CO_2	+300	0.4–2	0.1	33.3	Hjort et al. (2023)
Pt/CS/LOx	450 nm	+400	0.2–3	0.1	35.8	Madden et al. (2022)
PB/CS/LOx	CO_2	–50	0–5	0.25	6.1	Bauer et al. (2021b)
TTF/LOx-BSA-GA	450 nm	+150	4–20	2.4	12.4	this work
Screen/inject-printed						
PAni/PtNPs/LOx		+250	0.8–5	0.06	3.94	Li et al. (2018)
GMgOC-PVDF-NMP/LOx/CS-genipin		+100	1–50	–	14.5	Shitanda et al. (2023)
PB-LOxAuNPs-CS-PVC		+50	0.5–20	0.12	0.19	García-Guzmán et al. (2024)

GMgOC; Grafted MgO-templated carbon, NMP, 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone, PB; Prussian blue, PVC; polyvinyl chloride, PVDF; polyvinylidene fluoride hexafluoropropylene copolymer.

3.4. Performance evaluation of a dual-mode glucose and lactate biosensor

The successful development of individual glucose and lactate biosensors and the demonstrated robust performance for sensitive and selective detection in sweat highlights the potential of developed platforms for real-time, accurate monitoring of glucose and lactate levels. The next step was the development of a dual biosensor, bringing together the capabilities of the individual biosensors into a unified platform for simultaneous detection of both biomarkers. For this purpose, a dual sensing platform was designed on the polyimide film, featuring two working electrodes for lactate and glucose, along with a surrounding counter and reference electrodes (Fig. 5a). Subsequently, the LIG working electrodes were biofunctionalized with glucose and lactate recognition matrices, following the previously optimized protocols. The performance of the fabricated dual sensing platform was thoroughly evaluated using a FIA system in artificial sweat, with both sequential (Fig. 5d–f) and simultaneous (Fig. 5g–i) injections of the analytes. The sensitivities of the glucose sensing unit on the dual platform were $40.5 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2} \text{mM}^{-1}$ for sequential analysis and $41.2 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2} \text{mM}^{-1}$ for simultaneous detection, respectively. For the lactate sensing unit, the slopes were $11.9 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2} \text{mM}^{-1}$ and $12.0 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2} \text{mM}^{-1}$, respectively. Comparing these results with those from single biosensors

through paired *t*-test, demonstrated that the biosensing performance of each individual biosensor was preserved.

4. Conclusion

In this study, a dual biosensing platform was developed based on DLW of LIG electrodes on flexible polyimide films. Stable, highly efficient and reproducible LIG transducing elements were fabricated by careful selection of the laser writing instrumental settings followed by coating with TTF, which served both as LIG protective layer and redox mediator. The biofunctionalization steps of both glucose and lactate biosensors were also carefully optimized and the analytical characteristics of the resulting individual biosensors were comprehensively investigated. The developed biosensors showed wide linear range, with sensitivities and LODs comparable or superior to those reported in the literature both in buffer and artificial sweat media. Importantly for future practical applications, the proposed devices displayed impressive operational stability (approximately 2 h of continuous use) and long-term storage usability (over 8 weeks for the glucose biosensor and 4 weeks for the lactate biosensor). These characteristics were attributed to the protecting effect of the deposited TTF on LIG and the deposition of optimized encapsulation matrices, which prevented enzyme

Fig. 5. Schematic representation of a) the DLW dual LIG platform; b) biofunctionalization stages and c) detection mechanisms; d) FIA records for a dual glucose-lactate platform upon sequential injection of Glu and Lac standard solutions; sequential calibration curves for e) Glu and f) Lac in artificial sweat; g) FIA records of simultaneous Glu and Lac detection, with the corresponding calibration curves (h and i) in artificial sweat.

denaturation. Another outstanding feature of the biosensors was their selectivity, which enabled successful detection of the biomarkers in artificial sweat. This enhanced performance was attributed to the low applied potential and the presence of the Nafion layer. Following the successful evaluation of the individual biosensors, the acquired knowledge was effectively applied to develop the dual-platform system. Both glucose and lactate sensing units showed performance closely comparable to that of their respective individual biosensors. This feature further emphasizes robustness and enhances the platform potential for reliable, simultaneous detection of multiple biomarkers for practical applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Hassan Hamidi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Richard Murray:** Investigation. **Vincenzo Vezzoni:** Investigation. **Somayeh Bozorgzadeh:** Investigation. **Alan O’Riordan:** Writing – review & editing. **Daniele Pontiroli:** Writing – review & editing. **Mauro Riccò:** Investigation. **Aidan J. Quinn:** Writing – review & editing. **Daniela Iacopino:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosx.2025.100600>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Andrade, J.M., Estévez-Pérez, M.G., 2014. Statistical comparison of the slopes of two regression lines: a tutorial. *Anal. Chim. Acta* 838, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2014.04.057>.
- Asaduzzaman, M., Zahed, M.A., Sharifuzzaman, M., Reza, M.S., Hui, X., Sharma, S., Shin, Y., Do, Park, J.Y., 2023. A hybridized nano-porous carbon reinforced 3D graphene-based epidermal patch for precise sweat glucose and lactate analysis. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 219, 114846. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2022.114846>.
- Backiyalakshmi, G., Snehalatha, U., Salvador, A.L., 2024. Recent advancements in non-invasive wearable electrochemical biosensors for biomarker analysis - a review. *Anal. Biochem.* 692. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ab.2024.115578>.
- Bariya, M., Nyein, H.Y.Y., Javey, A., 2018. Wearable sweat sensors. *Nat. Electron.* 1, 160–171. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41928-018-0043-y>.
- Bauer, M., Wunderlich, L., Weinzierl, F., Lei, Y., Duerkop, A., Alshareef, H.N., Baeumner, A.J., 2021a. Electrochemical multi-analyte point-of-care perspiration sensors using on-chip three-dimensional graphene electrodes. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 413, 763–777. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-020-02939-4>.
- Bauer, M., Wunderlich, L., Weinzierl, F., Lei, Y., Duerkop, A., Alshareef, H.N., Baeumner, A.J., 2021b. Electrochemical multi-analyte point-of-care perspiration sensors using on-chip three-dimensional graphene electrodes. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 413, 763–777. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-020-02939-4>.

- Boeva, Z., Mousavi, Z., Sokalski, T., Bobacka, J., 2024. Recent trends in non-invasive on-body chemical sensing. *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.* 172, 117542. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2024.117542>.
- Curran, L.J., Sage, F.C., Hagedorn, M., Hamilton, L., Patrone, J., Gerasopoulos, K., 2018. Wearable sensor system for detection of lactate in sweat. *Sci. Rep.* 8, 15890. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-33565-x>.
- Gao, P., Kasama, T., Shin, J., Huang, Y., Miyake, R., 2022. A Mediated enzymatic electrochemical sensor using paper-based laser-induced graphene. *Biosensors* 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios12110995>.
- Gao, W., Emaminejad, S., Nyein, H.Y.Y., Challa, S., Chen, K., Peck, A., Fahad, H.M., Ota, H., Shiraki, H., Kiriya, D., Lien, D.-H., Brooks, G.A., Davis, R.W., Javey, A., 2016. Fully integrated wearable sensor arrays for multiplexed in situ perspiration analysis. *Nature* 529, 509–514. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature16521>.
- García-Guzmán, J.J., Jiménez Heras, J.M., López-Iglesias, D., González-Álvarez, R.J., Cubillana-Aguilera, L., González Macías, C., Fernández Alba, J.J., Palacios-Santander, J.M., 2024. New spin coated multilayer lactate biosensor for acidosis monitoring in continuous flow assisted with an electrochemical pH probe. *Microchim. Acta* 191, 526. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00604-024-06602-y>.
- Garland, N.T., Schmieder, J., Johnson, Z.T., Hjort, R.G., Chen, B., Andersen, C., Sanborn, D., Kjeldgaard, G., Pola, C.C., Li, J., Gomes, C., Smith, E.A., Angus, H., Meyer, J., Claussen, J.C., 2023. Wearable flexible perspiration biosensors using laser-induced graphene and polymeric tape microfluidics. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 15, 38201–38213. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.3c04665>.
- Hale, P.D., Liu, L.-F., Skotheim, T.A., 1991. Enzyme-modified carbon paste: tetrathiafulvalene electrodes for the determination of acetylcholine. *Electroanalysis* 3, 751–756. <https://doi.org/10.1002/elan.1140030805>.
- Hall, M.M., Rajasekaran, S., Thomsen, T.W., Peterson, A.R., 2016. Lactate: friend or foe. *PM&R* 8, S8–S15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmrj.2015.10.018>.
- Hamidi, H., Leveux, J., Larrigy, C., Russo, A., Vaughan, E., Murray, R., Quinn, A.J., Iacopino, D., 2023. Laser induced graphene (LIG) biosensors derived from chitosan: towards sustainable and green electronics. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* X 15, 100403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosx.2023.100403>.
- Hjort, R.G., Pola, C.C., Soares, R.R.A., Opere-Addo, J., Smith, E.A., Claussen, J.C., Gomes, C.L., 2023. Laser-induced graphene decorated with platinum nanoparticles for electrochemical analysis of saliva. *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* 6, 20801–20811. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsanm.3c03786>.
- Khosravi, S., Soltanian, S., Servati, A., Khademhosseini, A., Zhu, Y., Servati, P., 2023. Screen-printed textile-based electrochemical biosensor for noninvasive monitoring of glucose in sweat. *Biosensors*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios13070684>.
- Lei, Y., Zhao, W., Zhang, Y., Jiang, Q., He, J.-H., Baeumner, A.J., Wolfbeis, O.S., Wang, Z. L., Salama, K.N., Alshareef, H.N., 2019. A MXene-based wearable biosensor system for high-performance in vitro perspiration analysis. *Small* 15, 1901190. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.201901190>.
- Li, L., Pan, L., Ma, Z., Yan, K., Cheng, W., Shi, Y., Yu, G., 2018. All inkjet-printed amperometric multiplexed biosensors based on nanostructured conductive hydrogel electrodes. *Nano Lett.* 18, 3322–3327. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.8b00003>.
- Li, X., Yang, Y., Zhang, B., Lin, X., Fu, X., An, Y., Zou, Y., Wang, J.-X., Wang, Z., Yu, T., 2022. Lactate metabolism in human health and disease. *Signal Transduct. Target. Ther.* 7, 305. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-022-01151-3>.
- Liu, M., Yang, M., Wang, M., Wang, H., Cheng, J., 2022. A flexible dual-analyte electrochemical biosensor for salivary glucose and lactate detection. *Biosensors*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios12040210>.
- Liu, M., Zhao, G., Yang, C., Wang, H., Cheng, J., 2023. An enzymatic electrochemical biosensing interface developed by the laser-induced graphene electrode. *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* 10. <https://doi.org/10.1002/admi.202300235>.
- Liu, Shan, Li, X., Gan, L., Liu, Sutong, Luo, H., Du, X., Loufy, S.A., Tan, H., Guo, J., Li, C., 2024. Carbon-based implantable bioelectronics. *Appl. Phys. Rev.* 11, 31311. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0160168>.
- Madden, J., Vaughan, E., Thompson, M., O’ Riordan, A., Galvin, P., Iacopino, D., Rodrigues Teixeira, S., 2022. Electrochemical sensor for enzymatic lactate detection based on laser-scribed graphitic carbon modified with platinum, chitosan and lactate oxidase. *Talanta* 246, 123492. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2022.123492>.
- Meng, L., Chirtes, S., Liu, X., Eriksson, M., Mak, W.C., 2022. A green route for lignin-derived graphene electrodes: a disposable platform for electrochemical biosensors. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2022.114742>.
- Pinheiro, T., Silvestre, S., Coelho, J., Marques, A.C., Martins, R., Sales, M.G.F., Fortunato, E., 2021. Laser-Induced graphene on paper toward efficient fabrication of flexible, planar electrodes for electrochemical sensing. *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* 8, 2101502. <https://doi.org/10.1002/admi.202101502>.
- Sempionatto, J.R., Jeerapan, I., Krishnan, S., Wang, J., 2020. Wearable chemical sensors: emerging systems for on-body analytical chemistry. *Anal. Chem.* 92, 378–396. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.9b04668>.
- Settu, K., Chiu, P.-T., Huang, Y.-M., 2021. Laser-induced graphene-based enzymatic biosensor for glucose detection. *Polymers* 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13162795>.
- Shitanda, I., Ozono, Y., Morishita, Y., Matsui, H., Loew, N., Motosuke, M., Mukaimoto, T., Kobayashi, M., Mitsuhashi, T., Sugita, Y., Matsuo, K., Yanagita, S., Suzuki, T., Mikawa, T., Watanabe, H., Itagaki, M., 2023. Air-bubble-insensitive microfluidic lactate biosensor for continuous monitoring of lactate in sweat. *ACS Sens.* 8, 2368–2374. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssensors.3c00490>.
- Suginta, W., Khunkaewla, P., Schulte, A., 2013. Electrochemical biosensor applications of polysaccharides chitin and chitosan. *Chem. Rev.* 113, 5458–5479. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr300325r>.

- Tiliakos, A., Ceaus, C., Iordache, S.M., Vasile, E., Stamatin, I., 2016. Morphic transitions of nanocarbons via laser pyrolysis of polyimide films. *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis* 121, 275–286. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2016.08.007>.
- Vaughan, E., Larrigy, C., Burke, M., Sygellou, L., Quinn, A.J., Galiotis, C., Iacopino, D., 2020. Visible laser scribing fabrication of porous graphitic carbon electrodes: morphologies, electrochemical properties, and applications as disposable sensor platforms. *ACS Appl. Electron. Mater.* 2, 3279–3288. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaem.0c00612>.
- Vekic, J., Silva-Nunes, J., Rizzo, M., 2022. Glucose metabolism disorders: challenges and opportunities for diagnosis and treatment. *Metabolites*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/metabo12080712>.
- Wu, J., Liu, H., Chen, W., Ma, B., Ju, H., 2023. Device integration of electrochemical biosensors. *Nat. Rev. Bioeng.* 1, 346–360. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44222-023-00032-w>.
- Yang, M., Wang, H., Cheng, J., 2023. Continuous monitoring of multiple biomarkers with an ultrasensitive 3D-structured wearable biosensor. *Cell Reports Methods* 3, 100579. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crmeth.2023.100579>.
- Zahed, M.A., Barman, S.C., Das, P.S., Sharifuzzaman, M., Yoon, H.S., Yoon, S.H., Park, J. Y., 2020. Highly flexible and conductive poly (3, 4-ethylene dioxythiophene)-poly (styrene sulfonate) anchored 3-dimensional porous graphene network-based electrochemical biosensor for glucose and pH detection in human perspiration. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2020.112220>.
- Zhang, L., Wang, L., Li, J., Cui, C., Zhou, Z., Wen, L., 2022. Surface engineering of laser-induced graphene enables long-term monitoring of on-body uric acid and pH simultaneously. *Nano Lett.* 22, 5451–5458. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.2c01500>.
- Zhang, S., He, Z., Zhao, W., Liu, C., Zhou, S., Ibrahim, O.O., Wang, C., Wang, Q., 2024a. Innovative material-based wearable non-invasive electrochemical sweat sensors towards biomedical applications. *Nanomaterials* 14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano14100857>.
- Zhang, Z., Huang, L., Chen, Y., Qiu, Z., Meng, X., Li, Y., 2024b. Portable glucose sensing analysis based on laser-induced graphene composite electrode. *RSC Adv.* 14, 1034–1050. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d3ra06947h>.